

THE ASSESSMENT OF THE MOST FREQUENT INJURIES AND THEIR CAUSES IN PEOPLE PRACTICING SKATEBOARDING

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Summary

Introduction: Skateboarding is a physical activity more often chosen by young people. This is because there are more new skate parks in Poland- places where you can try your hand at riding a skateboard, roller skates or BMX bikes. Not without reason the sport has been included in the group of extreme sports.

The aim of the work: Aim of this study is to evaluate the most common type of injury to people riding on a skateboard and the reasons for their falls. The aim of the work is also to introduce issues related to traumas in skateboarding and drawing attention to the prevention of injuries in this sport.

Research material: The study referred to 30 people riding on a skateboard in a skatepark in Myslecinek, Bydgoszcz. Only male persons took part in the survey, aged from 11 years to 23 years. The average age in the study group was 16 years old.

Methods: The survey was conducted after obtaining the written consent of the respondent. In the case of underage skateboarders a written consent was required from the parent or legal guardian. In order to obtain answers we used a research technique in the form of the Questionnaire form and the method of observation. Respondents were asked to fill in the Questionnaire form. After receiving the questionnaires the answers were statistically processed, results were summarized and the conclusions were drawn.

Conclusions: On the basis of the conducted survey, there were the following conclusions created:

1. Skateboarding is a traumatic sport, and the most common injuries are fractures within the tibia, knees, elbows and wrists.
2. People practicing skateboarding in most cases experience the injuries of lower limb such as sprains of ankle and knee. Within the upper limb the most common injuries are fractures of the forearm and hand.
3. Head injuries in the skaters are rare.
4. The main cause of injuries in the skateboarders is lack of protectors, no warm-up before the ride, fatigue and inadequate physical preparation for the ride.
5. Lack of knowledge of the techniques of safe fall contributes to higher incidence of injuries in the group of skateboarders.
6. Persons practicing skateboarding after injuries such as bruises and sprains of ankle do not report to health centers to obtain medical assistance.
7. Lack of injury treatment contributes to the deepening of pathology, leading to further injuries and subsequently to health problems.
8. The main form of rehabilitation proceedings with a history of trauma are treatments of physiotherapy.

Introduction

Skateboarding is a physical activity more often chosen by young people. This is because in Poland there are more and more new skate parks, places where you can try your hand at riding a skateboard, roller skates or BMX bikes. Most of the scientific publication dedicated to skateboard was founded in the late 60's and 70's. Research on injuries among skateboarders to a large extent contributed to the bans on the sport in Sweden and Norway until the early 90's. Due to the occurrence of fatal accidents to children riding skateboards and frequent head injuries in the skaters apparent prohibition of this sport appeared. Often you can find the password "ban the boards" (the prohibition of skateboarding).

Present skateboarding differs significantly from that of the 30's. Today, skaters choose

skateparks more often than the streets as a place to ride. They have a wider choice of equipment and a variety of riding techniques. The most common injuries in them result from poorly conducted training that prepares them for shows and competitions, and less often from the fact of driving in the streets and collisions with pedestrians and cars [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Not without reason the sport has been included in the group of extreme sports. Injuries and contusions experienced while riding a skateboard led to numerous discussions about banning the skateboarding in many countries, especially among children under 12 years of age.

The causes of injuries while riding on a skateboard can be numerous. If skaters ignore the warm-up, the use of protectors, proper maintenance of equipment, environmental conditions and safe riding style the fall and injury rate may get higher. In skateboarding the lack of preparatory period and the warm-up is an important element influencing the susceptibility to injury. For people who have avoided sports so far and lead a sedentary lifestyle and they want to try their hand at riding a skateboard, the period of preparation is very important. It should last for at least six weeks before first going to the skatepark [3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12].

The aim of the work

The aim of this study is to evaluate the most common type of injury experienced by people riding on a skateboard and the reasons for their falls. The aim of the work is to introduce issues related to traumas in skateboarding and drawing attention to the prevention of injuries in this sport. The results of this study will help young people become aware of the importance of prevention, safety and protection of the body during a training ride on a skateboard in order to avoid harmful changes in the motoric system in adult life.

Research material

The study referred to 30 people riding on a skateboard in a skate park in Myslecinek, Bydgoszcz. The survey was conducted after obtaining the written consent of the respondents. In the case of underaged skaters, the consent of skateboarders' parent or legal guardian was required.

Only males participated in the survey as it was not possible to meet and test any female person skateboarding in the skatepark. Examined skateboarders were aged from 11 years to 23 years. The average age in the study group was 16 years old.

Skateboarders taking part in the study in one of the questions were asked to self-evaluate their riding skills on a skateboard. According to their own opinion, they assigned themselves to the group corresponding to the level of skillfulness: newcomers - people who were riding the skateboard for the first time during the period of the survey, novice skateboarders - recently started riding on a skateboard, intermediate group and advanced group.

In skateboarding, there are two types of riding. One of them is regular, with the skateboarder having the left leg in front of the board, and the right pushing back, or vice versa, but then the style is called "goofy" - then at the front of the board there is the right leg and the left leg is used for propelling the skateboard. Predisposition to a particular style of riding is related to the lateralization of the body (with domination of one hemisphere of the brain). Right-legged skateboarders usually choose regular riding style and their left hemisphere of the brain is dominating. Left-legged skaters prefer goofy style as their right hemisphere of the brain dominates. The same rule also applies to a hand or eye. Among the skaters participating in the study, 16 people (53%) rode a style of goofy, and 14 (47%) chose the regular style. None of the respondents did not report the predisposition to use both styles of riding in the same way.

Methods

In order to answer the questions a Questionnaire form was used as a research technique. Also the method of observation was applied.

In the first stage of the study, people taking part in it have been informed about the purpose of the study. After obtaining written consent from study participants (in the case of the underaged, a

parent or legal guardian of a child had to hand in a written consent), participants were asked to fill in the Questionnaire form. After receiving completed surveys the results were analyzed statistically, they were summarized and on this basis the conclusions were formulated.

Tests were conducted on healthy people riding on a skateboard, they were children, adolescents and adults. The study group consisted of 30 persons.

Questionnaire form was developed for the examination and it contained 27 questions. The Questionnaire form consisted of: conjunctive closed questions, which gave a choice of several responses, disjunctive closed questions - allowing to select only one response, semi-open questions that gave the respondent to choose from the proposed responses and select the field "other". The survey also included open-ended questions, allowing respondent to express personal response. In order to understand the environment of skateboarders, their techniques and tricks, the circumstances of falls in a better way, the skaters were observed without their knowledge. It helped to watch them ride in a natural and free way, without being tense and what influenced the objectivity of the observation results.

To elaborate the examination results statistically the *SAS Statistical Analysis System* was used. To determine the limit level of significance (p) of posed hypotheses different qualitative analysis tests were used. Fisher's exact test was the main determinant. The level of significance was $p < 0.05$ or $p = 0.05$. When $p > 0.05$ it was assumed that there is no correlation between the parameters studied. The results were presented in the following tables and charts.

Results

Chet Childress, a person known and respected in the skateboarding world, once said to a film director: "If you need a stunt, hire a skateboarder." Comparison of stunts to skateboarders is very relevant in terms of courage, physical fitness, the need for risk and adrenaline and also in less pleasant aspects, such as trauma and injuries. Tricks performed by skateboarders in skate parks could be easily compared to the stunts' work.

Despite the beneficial for our health aspects of the sport, one should always bear in mind the risk of injury. Injuries are probable while practicing any kind of sport, both at the occasional and regular physical activity. However, sport should never be ignored and all possible ways should be taken in order to be in a good health condition as long as it is possible.

The analysis of data from the questionnaire form has helped to characterize the causes of injury and thus it enabled to provide a method of avoiding the injuries.

People participating in the study were young people between 11 and 23 years of age. Persons aged 15 were the biggest group of respondents - 5 people (19%).

Fig. 1. The age of the respondents.

The studies did not refer to persons over the age of 23 what may indicate that mainly schoolchildren and students practice skateboarding.

The time during which skaters ride on a skateboard was not more than 10 years. This shows the popularity of this sport especially among young people and the fact that it has recently spread

widely in Poland. 12 people (40%) of respondents reported that they ride a skateboard for over 3 years, what means that they began their adventure with skateboarding before the indoor skate park in Bydgoszcz was built.

Fig. 2. Respondents division according to the period of practicing skateboarding.

Fig. 3. Skateboarders division according to their level of abilities – subjective.

The figure above (fig. 3) shows the division of skateboarders due to the subjective evaluation of their riding skills. Most of the respondents assessed their riding at a very high level, as the intermediate - 15 people (50%) or advanced - 10 people (34%). Only one person called himself a novice. This situation indicates that young skaters from Bydgoszcz practice a lot since the skate park was built and their high skills are worth of admiration.

Among skateboarders from Bydgoszcz as many as 28 people (93%) said that the skateboard was properly chosen, only one person noted that on the day of the survey he had inadequate equipment to ride. One skateboarder did not know what the proper selection of skateboards was and whether his board met the criteria for safety.

Fig. 4. Respondents division according to the proper choice of the skateboard type.

One of the hypotheses presented for the research problem was the lack of warm-up before

riding for the frequency of injury occurrence. The chart below shows that the warm-up is used regularly before riding by 11 respondents (17%), only one of them warms up occasionally, and 18 respondents (60%) never perform a warm-up before training. Appropriate preparation of the body to physical exertion, such as skateboard training is very important for our health and it can help to prevent injuries.

Fig. 5. Performing the warm-up before the ride.

Most of the examined participants, that is 18 people (60%) did not carry out warm-up before the ride. They explained their behavior with laziness or the lack of knowledge how it should be carried out.

Limited education of young people in school physical education, a lack of discussion over topics of safe sport and the negligence from the supervisors of skate parks result in the fact that young people decide about their skateboard training alone. Often with lack of knowledge, and because of ambition and perseverance in the pursuit of excellence in riding young people harm themselves.

Fig. 6. The reasons for Lack of warm-up before the ride.

Another important problem is the lack of protective equipment among young people riding around in skateboard parks. From the observations and the survey it is noticed that only 6 respondents (20%) use protective equipment. Most of respondents of that small group pointed to the carefully selected shoes with thicker soles and ankle stabilization (however, without any further protection was mentioned). Only 4 persons (13 %) used helmets and only one person (3%) had a complete set of pads on the joints of limbs and a helmet.

Fig. 7. Using protective equipment by the skaters.

The knowledge of safe fall techniques was also assessed. During the first steps on a skateboard it is extremely important to get familiar with the probability of falls and with physical and mental preparation for this situation. The golden rule of safe skateboard falls refers to approaching the center of body gravity as close to the ground as possible, relaxing muscles, putting chin closer to the breastbone and keeping loose hands close to the body (never straight at the elbows) and trying to direct the collapse to the side or front of the body. 15 people (50%) answered that they did not know the techniques of secure falls, one person (3%) did not know that there was such a technique, and 14 people (47%) said that they could safely fall down.

Fig. 8. Using the technique of safe fall among the skaters.

During the survey skateboarders were asked about their riding style, whether it was dangerous and about risks while riding in a skate park or elsewhere. They were also asked to assess whether their riding might pose a threat to their health and to other people. 47% admitted for hazardous and dangerous riding, 33% considered their driving to be safe, while 20% had difficulty in assessing.

In the survey, there was also the question concerning the skateboard training. Skateboarders had to indicate whether when they feel tired while riding on a skateboard they stop or continue the ride and the trick learning. Although fatigue did not interrupt the workout 20 skaters (67%) despite the fatigue did not interrupt the workout, 10 respondents - (33%) resigns from further riding.

Fig. 9. The skaters' behavior during the training despite the fatigue.

The table below presents the injuries that occurred in skateboarding in the joints of upper and lower extremities. It can be noticed that the bruises are an integral part of skateboarding training. They represent 76% of injuries in the joints, and each of the respondents indicated the occurrence of bruises in at least two areas of the body.

Tab. I. The most frequent joint injuries in skaters.

The number of people	Arm joint	Elbow joint	Wrist and palm joints	Hip joint	Knee joint	Ankle joint	n
No injury	15 (18%)	17 (20%)	16 (19%)	15 (18%)	9 (10%)	10(12%)	82
Dislocation	2 (22%)	1 (11%)	2 (22%)	0	0	44 (44%)	9
Bruise	13 (17%)	12 (16%)	12 (16%)	15 (20%)	14 (18%)	9 (12%)	75
Sprain	0	0	0	0	7 (50%)	7(50%)	14

11 patients (36%) also reported injuries in the form of fractures. Frequently the fractures concerned the palm (27%), ulna (28%) and radial bone (18%). Individuals broke clavicle (9%), rib (9%) and tibia (9%).

Fig. 10. The localization of fractures in respondents.

Respondents in one of the survey questions were asked to identify the most common causes of injury for skateboarders. Most people - 19 (63%) indicated the bravado and risky riding and performing of tricks. Other reasons were as follows: the need to impress others (43%), inadequately prepared area to ride (43%) and dangerous behavior of others (43%). Lack of protectors was

identified by 11 people (36%). The beginnings of skateboarding learning and small skateboarding skills as the risk of injury were pointed out by 8 people (26%). The smallest group of respondents chose poorly matched skateboard and weak physical preparation of the body to ride as the reasons of injury occurrence.

Fig. 11. Causes of injuries in skaters – subjective assessment.

The study also assessed the treatment and physiotherapy procedures after the recovery from injuries. The questionnaire contained open-ended questions, asking about the information on all forms of treatment and rehabilitation after experienced trauma. 32% of respondents who have experienced trauma stated no form of treatment, and the remaining 68% described the medical interventions to their own injuries. 30% of those treated were rehabilitated in medical centers.

Fig. 12. Skaters division according to medical intervention in case of injury.

Fig. 13. Physiotherapeutic methods applied after the injury recovery.

Fig. 13 shows physiotherapy methods indicated by skateboarders used in order to accelerate their return to fitness. 8 patients were rehabilitated (26%). Among them, 5 patients (62%) underwent more than one method of rehabilitation. All respondents who had used kinesiotherapy, had also performed physiotherapy. Two persons (6%) pointed kinesio taping as the supporting method - one of them had a twisted ankle and the other had a twisted knee with collateral ligament and anterior cruciate ligament rupture. 2 patients (6%) used PNF method, the remaining skateboarders performed exercises on a bicycle and a stepper and also relieving exercises, isometric exercises, and exercises with resistance. Only two people from nineteen patients who had trauma with damage of the ligaments of the joint underwent the balance exercises and proprioception training. One person has been rehabilitated with the use of methods of manual therapy.

Fischer's exact test showed that there had been significant relationship between wearing protectors by skateboarders, and the occurrence of joints (excluding bruises). (**p= 0.01686**).

Tab. II. Freq procedure – Dependence between usage of protectors and joint injuries (excluding bruises).

Using protectors	Joint injuries excluding bruises		
	No injury	Injury occurred	Total
Amount			
Percentage of listed lines			
Percentage of listed columns			
Lack of protectors	8 33.33% 61.54%	16 66.66% 94.11%	24
Used protectors	5 83.33% 39.46%	1 16.66% 5.99%	6
Totals	13	17	30

Fisher's exact test	
Cell (1.1) amount(F)	8
Left-sided pr. <= F	0.09916
Right-sided pr. >= F	0.00843
Table of probability (P)	0.0759
Two-sided pr. <= P	0.01686

Skateboarding with the protectors: this paper states the hypothesis that the lack of protectors makes the injury occurrence more probable. Among those who wore pads there were no injuries such as: contusions, hematomas and abrasions on the protected area.

The statistical correlation occurred ($p < 0.05$) when data on the number of people now wearing protectors was compared to the number of those patients who had a history of fractures or sprains $p = 0.04$. People who have already suffered from skateboarding trauma resulting from riding without protectors today are trying to protect already damaged areas. Injured skateboarders, who experienced repeated ankle sprain are currently riding in shoes that stabilize the joint. People after surgical reconstruction of the damaged knee ligaments use knee protectors to reduce the risk of further injury and trauma-related injury. From this correlation it can be concluded that the unpleasant experience causes prevention from further injury. These people can be recognized as a good example for their colleagues, who unfortunately do not use protective equipment.

There was a significant correlation noted between the frequency of falls and wearing protectors. The survey revealed that none of the people wearing pads did not fall down very often, and only one person indicated frequent falls. The other people stated that they rarely fell. These individuals also claimed that they are familiar with the technique of safe falling and they were able to apply it. This correlation may indicate that these people have a greater experience and are better prepared for the ride. This group of skaters showed the best technical preparation and 87% of them described their riding as advanced.

Most of people wearing pads also said that they performed a warm-up and that it happened to them to continue training despite the fatigue. A large group of people riding in the protective pads indicated that their riding was dangerous and risky (75%). Among the respondents there was no correlation between wearing protective equipment and the length of skateboarding ride period. In this case the frequency would be more important.

Warm-up performed before skateboarding: the correlation occurred between people who do not carry out the warm-up and those who have suffered more than one injury within the musculoskeletal system. People who carry out the warm-up did not indicate the damage of soft tissues (such as rupture, strain and overload). The average age of people warming up before riding the skateboard was 18 years old. Warm-up was carried out only among the older skaters, younger skateboarders were not aware of the importance of preparation and warming up the body before physical effort on a skateboard.

The incidence of falls among skateboarders: among people who indicated that they fall very often, each had a history of injuries more serious than abrasions and contusions. None of these skaters did not ride in a helmet and only two indicated that they could safely fall, one of them correctly described the technique of secure falls.

Risky skateboarding: There was a correlation between people who indicated that their riding was dangerous and risky for them and the environment and the type of injury they suffered. These people indicated the biggest number of bruises and damages of soft tissues.

Discussion

Skateboarding is a most popular sport among young people, which was confirmed by tests carried out and the results presented by Rethnam, Forsman and Eriksson.

According to Rethnam average age of the skater was 15 years old and for the 50 wounded skateboarders there were 40 male skaters. In a study published in the article by Forsmana and

Eriksson, half of the people surveyed were aged 13 to 16 years and 95% were male skaters [66, 67].

The survey shows that 100% of respondents had suffered a contusion injury, wounds or abrasions. The articles mentioned above cover studies in orthopedics and emergency departments in the University Hospital in Sweden Umeå for the period of 1995-1998 and in the Glan Clwyd Clinic in the UK in the period of 2002-2006. These studies did not include measurements of minor injuries such as bruises which rarely require hospital treatment. Both articles focused on serious injuries apart from soft tissue injuries. However, it was noted that contusions in the form of bruises and wounds that did not require medical consultation were numerous.

The study shows that in the case of upper extremity injuries there fracture predominated in 63%, whereas sprains and dislocations, which were the most numerous among the respondents referred to the joints of the lower limbs in 79%. The obtained results do not differ from the results of studies conducted in Sweden where the survey showed that the most common injuries concerned legs and they took the form of dislocations and sprains (44%). Fractures concerned the upper limb bones.

British studies from the years of 2003 - 2005 showed that most injuries involved the upper limb. The fracture of upper limb represented 60% of all injuries of upper limb and the remaining injuries involved soft tissue. These results cover our observations.

Fractures accounted for 69% of the lower limb injuries. Sprains and dislocations were in the minority of this area injuries. British research pointed to the occurrence of more fractures of the distal shin bone than of sprains around the ankle.

The study shows that most fractures referred to the ulna (35%), palm bones (35%), fracture of the radial bone (20%) and clavicle (10%).

The Rethnam's data from the years 2002-2006 shows that most common type of injury were fractures within the distal part of forearm bone and palm bones. There have been nine cases of fractures of distal part of radius bone fractures, 6 cases of fractures of phalanges, 5-fractures in the MP joints. There were no fractures of the scaphoid. Among our respondents there were no injuries in the MP and phalangeal joints.

In studies conducted in the area of lower extremity only fractures of the tibia were reported, which accounted for 9% of all fractures. In studies of Forsman and Eriksson from the years of 1995-1998 there were 8 cases of fractures within the ankle-bone and tibia fibula reported.

None of the respondents experienced metatarsal bone fracture, which was recorded in the Swedish study as the second most common injury in the lower limb. In the Rethnam's article discussing traumatism in skateboarding in the years 2002-2006 also fractures within the ankle in 5 cases and the tibia in one person were stated.

Among the results obtained from the survey there were no head injuries and severe back injury noticed. Two skaters pointed to contusion of sacrum and coccyx. In Rethnam's studies no head injuries neither open fractures no cervical spine injuries were noted.

In studies of Forsman and Eriksson there were only 4 cases of shock among the 136 wounded, which occurred at the youngest age group (0-9 years). The complete absence of head injuries in the data for the years 2002-2006 may be due to the fact that these injuries were not treated in hospitals.

On the basis of the above results it can be stated that skateboarding is not a dangerous sport which threatens life. In both articles there were no people mentioned who experienced permanent disability. In a study from the year 2002-2006 there was one casualty mentioned however the fatal accident happened due to road collision. According to Eriksson and Forsman most injuries were assigned to AIS 1 group, the so-called low risk, and the average frequency of injuries on a skateboard during the year was calculated to 10 cases.

Kujawiak described that 80% of skateboarding injuries occur within the upper limbs and the most common type of fracture refers to the ulnar ridge. Moreover, to major injuries added trauma of the cervical spine and injuries of acromial joint. According to the author, a serious risk is associated with head injuries, which represent 9% of all cases.

In a survey the respondents most frequently cited immobilization - 80% as the method of treatment. Plaster cast immobilization was pointed from all other forms by seven people, 8 people used elastic band and 3 people named leg stabilizer.

On the basis of results analysis it can be stated that the bruises and injuries are the predominant injury in skateboarders. Skaters do not wear protectors and their lack causes numerous damages while riding on a skateboard. The available literature does not report any data concerning the development of degeneration changes in people practicing skateboarding who can develop such changes as a result of injuries and micro damages.

Another aspect raised in this study is the issue warm-up. None of the articles studies the effects of the warm-up on the skateboarders' injuries. After reading many publications on the warm-up before the intended exercise, it can be concluded that the lack of preparation of muscles and tendons before riding on a skateboard may have an effect on injuries experienced by skaters. Before riding the skateboard it is important to stretch muscles in order to improve their elasticity and regeneration, as well as stretching proper conduct.

The results proved that the skateboarders are generally young people. 76% of the group consisted of people aged between 12 and 17 years. Similar results were obtained by Rethnam, Frosmann and Eriksson. Therefore it can be concluded that people who train a sport are often immature mentally and do not realize the consequences of irresponsible riding.

The studies showed that the lack of padding on skateboarders (80%), lack of warm-up (60%), short breaks for regeneration and continuation of skateboarding despite the fatigue (67%) have an impact on the incidence of injuries. All of these factors are among the causes of injuries in this sport [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27].

Conclusions

1. Skateboarding a sport prone to injuries and the most frequent injuries refer to bruises of tibia, knees, elbows and wrists.
2. In people practicing skateboarding the prevalent injuries concern lower limbs, and they take the form of sprain of ankles and knees. As far as upper limbs are concerned fractures of forearms and palms are the most frequent.
3. The main cause of skaters injuries are: lack of protectors, Lack of warm-up before the ride, fatigue, improper physical preparation for the ride.
4. Lack of knowledge of safe fall technique leads to frequent injuries in skateboarders.
5. People practicing skateboarding do not report themselves to medical clinics to gain Professional medical help.
6. Lack of injury treatment leads to deeper pathology and other injuries and as a consequence to following health problems.
7. Rehabilitation process after injuries does not always obey the rules of complexity, continuance and earliness.
8. The main form of rehabilitation is physiotherapy.

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